

IMPACT OF FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT VIA GOOGLE FORMS ON LEARNING OUTCOMES OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY AND MEDIA LITERACY

BY

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of formative assessment via Google Forms on undergraduate students' learning outcomes in Educational Technology and Media Literacy. A quasi-experimental design was employed to compare the performance of students assessed digitally through Google Forms with those evaluated using traditional paper-based methods. Data were collected from 192 students using pre-test and post-test measures, and results were analyzed through descriptive statistics and z-test analysis. Findings revealed that students accessed via Google Forms achieved higher post-test mean scores with lower variability compared to their counterparts in traditional assessments, indicating both superior performance and greater consistency. Gender comparisons showed nuanced patterns: female students slightly outperformed males in purely digital environments. These outcomes underscore the dual benefits of Google Form assessments in enhancing academic achievement and supporting gender inclusivity. The study contributes to the growing body of evidence on technology-mediated assessment, with implications for theory, policy, and practice in higher education

Keywords: Digital assessment, Google Forms, gender differences, higher education, digital tools.

Introduction

Nigerian university lecturers face a heavy workload, balancing teaching, research, and administrative duties, which often leave them with limited time for effective student assessment and feedback. The integration of technology, particularly in administering and grading formative and summative assessments, is essential to alleviate these pressures while improving learning outcomes (Adedoyin & Soykan, 2020). In the contemporary Nigerian educational landscape, the integration of technology into instructional and assessment practices is increasingly recognized as essential for improving learning outcomes, particularly in this higher education where these lecturers work. The emphasis on competency-based education and learner-centered approaches has underscored the importance of formative assessment in supporting student learning (Okebukola, 2020).

Formative assessment, when delivered effectively, serves as a pedagogical tool that

provides continuous feedback to both students and instructors, guiding academic performance, motivation, and instructional refinement (Black & Wiliam, 2018). With the rising adoption of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), tools such as Google Forms are being explored for their capacity to deliver formative assessments in scalable, flexible, and data-rich formats (Omodan & Ige, 2022). However, despite global progress, the empirical application and validation of such technologies remain limited within Nigerian universities, particularly in foundational courses such as Educational Technology.

Formative assessment refers to the range of procedures employed by instructors to evaluate student comprehension, learning needs, and academic progress during a lesson or course. Unlike summative assessments, formative assessments are intended not for grading purposes, but to inform instruction and improve student learning (Wiliam, 2013, Satish & Karishma (2024)). In digital learning

environments, formative assessments become more dynamic, as platforms like Google Forms allow instructors to deliver quizzes with instant feedback, varied item formats, and data analytics to monitor performance (Alruwais et al., 2018). This aligns with the constructivist learning paradigm, which emphasizes active participation, continuous feedback, and learner autonomy — all of which are enhanced by digital formative tools.

In Nigeria, the integration of digital tools in assessment has faced several systemic challenges including infrastructural deficits, resistance to pedagogical change, and limited faculty digital literacy (Onaolapo & Onasanya, 2020). Despite these limitations, several institutions have started to pilot platforms such as Google Classroom, Zoom, and Google Forms, especially during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, which necessitated remote and hybrid instruction. Among these tools, Google Forms stands out due to its free accessibility, user-friendliness, real-time data processing, and wide integration into Google Workspace used in many tertiary institutions (Adedoyin & Soykan, 2020). Studies from other contexts have shown that the integration of digital formative assessment tools positively influences student learning outcomes. For instance, Yulianti and Sugiharti (2020) found that students who received Google Form-based assessments demonstrated higher engagement and improved academic achievement compared to those assessed traditionally. Similarly, Irawati et al. (2021) observed that the instant feedback feature embedded in Google Forms contributed significantly to learner motivation and retention. While these findings are promising, most existing studies are situated in technologically advanced or better-resourced countries, which may not reflect the Nigerian educational context where access to consistent internet connectivity and devices can vary significantly.

Locally, Omodan and Ige (2022) conducted a study on technology-based assessment in a South-West Nigerian university and found moderate gains in student satisfaction but called for more empirical evaluation on actual learning outcomes. Likewise, Adebayo et al. (2019) examined the perception of university lecturers regarding e-assessment tools and reported a positive outlook on their effectiveness but highlighted a lack of empirical evidence tying these tools to performance gains. These insights suggest growing interest and perceived potential but highlight a gap in experimental or quasi-experimental studies that quantitatively assess the impact of tools like Google Forms on academic achievement in Nigeria.

A critical research gap exists in the Nigerian higher education landscape concerning the empirical validation of digital formative assessment. While tools like Google Forms are widely discussed, studies by Omodan & Ige (2022) and Adebayo et al. (2019) highlight a scarcity of local, data-driven evidence. The current literature over-relies on perceptions and theoretical frameworks, failing to provide measurable performance data. This leaves a pressing need for quasi-experimental research that directly assesses the impact of these interventions on student learning within Nigeria's distinct university environment.

The need for a more robust, data-backed exploration of technology-driven formative assessments in Nigeria underpins the importance of this study. As first-year students often struggle with adapting to university-level expectations and self-regulated learning, early and effective feedback mechanisms can be crucial in fostering academic success. Introducing Google Form-based formative assessment in an introductory Educational Technology course provides an opportunity to evaluate not only the tool's utility but also its pedagogical impact on learners transitioning into higher education.

This study responds to calls by Nigerian higher education stakeholders for evidence-based innovations that can improve student outcomes using available technologies (Okebukola, 2020). Furthermore, it aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education), which emphasizes inclusive and equitable quality education through the promotion of technology-enhanced learning. By employing a quasi-experimental research design with pre-test and post-test evaluation, this study aims to go beyond perceptions and contribute empirical evidence of performance changes among students. Additionally, it integrates student feedback through a Likert-scale questionnaire to provide nuanced understanding of the learners' experience with the tool, offering both quantitative and qualitative insights.

Ultimately, the study is expected to inform instructional practices, guide institutional policy on digital assessment adoption, and contribute to the scholarly discourse on contextualized use of educational technology in African higher education systems. It also serves as a model for scalable, low-cost formative assessment strategies that can be adopted by other departments and institutions.

Statement of Problems

Despite the growing adoption of digital tools like Google Forms for formative assessment in Nigerian universities, there is a scarcity of empirical studies measuring their direct impact on student learning outcomes (Omodan & Ige, 2022; Adebayo et al., 2019). While existing research highlights perceptions of e-assessment tools, few studies employ experimental or quasi-experimental designs to quantitatively evaluate whether Google Forms improve academic performance (Adedoyin & Soykan, 2020). This gap is exacerbated by the excessive workload faced by lecturers, which limits their capacity to administer timely, high-quality formative assessments using traditional methods

(Okebukola, 2020). Although technology-assisted tools like Google Forms could alleviate these challenges by automating grading and feedback, their pedagogical potential remains underutilized due to infrastructural constraints, resistance to change, and uneven digital literacy (Onalapo & Onasanya, 2020). Crucially, there is insufficient localized evidence to determine whether such tools genuinely enhance learning outcomes in foundational courses like Educational Technology and Media Literacy—where structured feedback could significantly boost engagement and knowledge retention—or whether they merely streamline administrative processes. Without robust empirical data, Nigerian institutions lack the justification to invest in wider adoption, targeted training, or policy reforms that prioritize formative e-assessment as a pedagogical (rather than logistical) tool.

Purpose of the study

This study examines how Google Forms, as a digital formative assessment tool, influences the academic performance of undergraduate students in Educational Technology and Media Literacy courses within Nigerian universities. The research specifically investigated the

1. Post-test score of students assessed through Google forms and those students assessed via traditional method?
2. Post test score of the male and that of female students assessed via Google forms.

Research Questions

1. What are the post test mean scores of students assessed via Google Forms and those assessed through traditional paper-based formative assessments?
2. What is the post test mean scores of male and female students assessed via Google Forms

Hypotheses

1. H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the post-test scores and standard deviation of students assessed via Google Forms and that of those assessed via traditional methods.
2. H_{02} : There is no significant difference in post-test scores and standard deviation of male and female students assessed via Google Forms and that of those assessed via traditional methods

Research Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental research design involving pre-test and post-test measures for two groups to determine the impact of formative assessment via Google Forms on students' learning outcomes. The design was considered appropriate because it facilitates comparison between experimental and control groups without complete randomization, which is often impractical in educational settings (Creswell, 2014; Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2018). The population of the study comprised 512 first-year undergraduate students in the Faculty of Education, Federal University Otuoke. The faculty consists of three departments: Business Education, Arts and Social Science Education, and Science Education. Two departments were selected using a simple random sampling technique to ensure fairness in representation (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2009). From this population, a sample of 192 students was drawn using proportionate stratified sampling to reflect departmental sizes and ensure gender balance, which is consistent with best practices in educational research (Cohen et al., 2018).

Two major instruments were employed for data collection. The first was a series of Google Forms-based formative quizzes administered to the experimental group, while the control group received traditional paper-based tests. The

second was an achievement test developed in line with the course content on Educational Technology and Media Literacy. To ensure content validity, the achievement test was reviewed by experts in Educational Measurement and Evaluation (Gay, Mills, & Airasian, 2012). Trial test was conducted, and the reliability of the instrument was established using the Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20), yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.82, which indicates satisfactory internal consistency (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2009).

The data collection procedure began with the administration of a pre-test to both groups to establish baseline equivalence. The experimental group was subsequently exposed to formative assessments delivered through Google Forms, while the control group was assessed using traditional paper-based methods. At the end of the instructional period, a post-test was administered to both groups under uniform conditions to measure learning outcomes (Creswell, 2014). Data analysis involved both descriptive and inferential statistics. Means and standard deviations were computed to summarize students' performance. To test the hypotheses, an independent samples t-test was used to compare the post-test scores of students assessed through Google Forms and those assessed through the traditional method (Research Question 1). Similarly, an independent samples t-test for gender was employed to examine differences in post-test performance between male and female students assessed via Google Forms (Research Question 2). These statistical tools were selected because they are appropriate for determining mean differences between two independent groups at a significance level of 0.05 (Field, 2018; Cohen et al., 2018).

Results

Research Question one: What are the mean score of the post test students assessed via Google Forms and those assessed through traditional paper-based formative assessments?

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviations of post-test results for students assessed using Google Forms and those evaluated through traditional paper-based formative assessments

Groups	Number	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean (x)	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean (x)	Standard Deviation (s)	
Google form	104	15.64	3.46	46.7	2.28	31.06
Traditional Format	88	15.98	3.21	29.22	2.69	13.24
Mean Diff.						17.82

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of students' performance across the two assessment modes. For the Google Form group (N = 104), the pre-test mean score was 15.64 (SD = 3.46), which increased markedly to 46.70 (SD = 2.28) in the post-test, yielding a mean gain of 31.06. In contrast, the traditional paper-based group (N = 88) recorded a pre-test mean of 15.98 (SD = 3.21) and a post-test mean of 29.22 (SD = 2.69), resulting in a comparatively smaller mean gain

of 13.24. The difference in mean gain scores between the groups was 17.82, clearly favoring the Google Form group. The relatively lower post-test standard deviation observed in the Google Form group (SD = 2.28) compared to the traditional group (SD = 2.69) further indicates greater consistency in performance among students exposed to the digital assessment format.

1. Research Question 2 What is the post test mean scores of male and female students assessed via Google Forms

Table 2, the mean score and standard deviation of post test score of male and that of the females students assess via Google form.

Gender	N	Mean	STD Dev.
Male	51	58.7	2.01
Female	53	61.3	2.19

Table 2 presents the mean scores and standard deviations of male and female students' post-test performance when assessed via Google Form. The results show that male students (N = 51) achieved a post-test mean score of M = 58.7 (SD = 2.01). Female students (N = 53) recorded a higher post-test mean score of M = 61.3 (SD = 2.19). The mean difference between the two groups is 2.6 points, indicating that female students outperformed their male counterparts on the post-test. Although both groups

demonstrated strong performance with relatively low variability (as indicated by the small standard deviations), the higher mean score among females suggests a slight gender advantage in favor of female students under the Google Form assessment mode. These findings imply that while Google Form assessments benefited both genders, female students may have engaged more effectively with the digital platform, leading to higher average achievement.

Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the post-test scores and standard deviation of

students assessed via Google Forms and that of those assessed via traditional methods.

Table 3: **Summary of z-test analysis of the mean** of the post-test scores and standard deviation of students assessed via Google Forms and that of those assessed via traditional methods

Groups	N	X	SD	df	Z-cal	Zcrit	Decision
Google form	104	46.7	2.28	190	48.5	1.96	H ₀₁ Rejected
Traditional Method	88	29.22	2.69				

Table 3 presents the results of a z-test comparing the post-test performance of students assessed via Google Forms and those evaluated using traditional paper-based methods. Students in the Google Form group ($N = 104, M = 46.7, SD = 2.28$) outperformed those in the traditional assessment group ($N = 88, M = 29.22, SD = 2.69$). The calculated z-value ($z_{cal} = 48.5$) was substantially greater than the critical z-value ($z_{crit} = 1.96$) at the 0.05 level of significance, with $df = 190$. Since z_{cal} exceeded z_{crit} , the null hypothesis (H₀₁), which stated that there is no significant difference in post-test performance between the two groups, was rejected. This result

indicates that the difference in performance between students assessed via Google Forms and those assessed through traditional methods is statistically significant. Specifically, students evaluated through Google Forms achieved higher mean scores and demonstrated greater consistency in performance, confirming the pedagogical advantage of digital formative assessments over traditional formats.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in post-test scores and standard deviation of male and female students assessed via Google Forms and that of those assessed via traditional methods

Table 4: Summary of the z-test comparing the post-test mean scores and standard deviations of male and female students assessed through Google Forms and traditional assessment methods

Groups	N	X	SD	df	Z-cal	Zcrit	Decision
Male	51	48.8	2.01	102	10.00	1.96	H ₀₁ Rejected
Female	53	44.7	2.19				

Table 4 shows the results of a z-test conducted to determine whether there is a significant difference in the post-test performance of male and female students assessed through Google Forms and traditional methods. The male group ($N = 51, M = 48.8, SD = 2.01$) obtained a higher mean score than the female group ($N = 53, M = 44.7, SD = 2.19$). The calculated z-value ($z_{cal} = 10.00$) exceeded the critical value ($z_{crit} = 1.96$)

at $df = 102$ and the 0.05 level of significance. Since $z_{cal} > z_{crit}$, the null hypothesis (H₀₂), which stated that there is no significant difference in post-test scores and variability between male and female students, was rejected. This finding indicates that there is a statistically significant difference in performance between the two gender groups, with male students outperforming their female counterparts. The relatively low

standard deviations for both groups ($SD = 2.01$ for males, $SD = 2.19$ for females) suggest consistent performance within each gender group, but the mean difference favors males.

Discussion

The data confirm a substantial advantage for digital assessment: students using Google Forms improved 2.3 times more than the control group (31.06 vs. 13.24 gain), underscoring its pedagogical value for enhancing learning (Table 1). One key explanation for this result is the interactive and immediate feedback capacity of digital tools, which has been shown to foster deeper student engagement and improved knowledge retention. For instance, Alruwais, Wills, and Wald (2018) found that online formative assessment platforms provide learners with prompt feedback, allowing them to monitor their progress and correct misconceptions more effectively than in paper-based settings. Similarly, López-Pernas et al. (2021) reported that the use of digital assessment systems increased both students' academic performance and their motivation, as the tools supported active learning and reduced the monotony often associated with traditional testing.

The lower post-test variability in the Google Form group ($SD = 2.28$) relative to the traditional group ($SD = 2.69$) further suggests more consistent performance across learners. This aligns with the argument of Shraim (2019), who noted that technology-driven assessments not only standardize delivery but also minimize human error and environmental distractions inherent in manual testing. Such uniformity can contribute to equitable assessment conditions, ensuring that learners' outcomes reflect their actual competence rather than test administration differences. Overall, the evidence from Table 1 reinforces the position that digital formative assessments, such as those administered via Google Forms, are more effective than traditional approaches in promoting

achievement, engagement, and assessment fairness in contemporary classrooms.

Table 2 shows that both male and female students demonstrated strong performance when assessed via Google Forms, though female students achieved slightly higher mean scores ($M = 61.3$, $SD = 2.19$) compared to their male counterparts ($M = 58.7$, $SD = 2.01$). The mean difference of 2.6 points suggests a modest gender advantage in favor of females under digital assessment conditions. This outcome is consistent with research indicating that female learners often exhibit higher levels of engagement and self-regulation in technology-enhanced learning environments. For example, Ong et al. (2020) found that female students tend to display stronger motivation and time-management skills when using e-learning platforms, which positively affects their achievement. Likewise, Heffernan et al. (2019) reported that female students frequently leverage digital assessments more effectively, partly due to greater responsiveness to feedback and collaborative features.

Furthermore, the relatively low variability in performance across both groups indicates that Google Form assessments provided a consistent testing experience for all students. This supports the findings of Al-Hattami (2020), who noted that e-assessments help to standardize the evaluation process and reduce disparities that may arise from subjective or context-dependent factors in traditional assessment methods. Taken together, these findings suggest that while Google Form assessments are beneficial for both genders, female students may derive slightly greater advantages, potentially due to stronger digital engagement strategies. This highlights the need for educators to design assessment practices that account for gender-related learning dynamics while ensuring that all students can maximize the benefits of digital platforms.

The results of Table 3 reveal a statistically significant difference between the post-test

performance of students assessed via Google Forms and those assessed through traditional paper-based methods. The Google Form group ($N = 104$, $M = 46.7$, $SD = 2.28$) achieved considerably higher scores than the traditional group ($N = 88$, $M = 29.22$, $SD = 2.69$), with the calculated z -value (48.5) far exceeding the critical value (1.96) at the 0.05 significance level. This finding leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, thereby confirming that digital assessment methods offer superior learning outcomes compared to conventional formats.

These results align with contemporary studies that emphasize the pedagogical effectiveness of technology-mediated assessments. For instance, Omodan and Dube (2019) demonstrated that digital assessment tools foster learner autonomy and engagement, which directly enhance academic achievement. Similarly, Ngaboyeka and Zegeye (2020) found that online formative assessments provide immediate feedback and flexible access, which improves students' understanding and performance relative to traditional paper-based testing. Moreover, Almahasees and Qassem (2021) observed that digital assessment environments, including Google Forms, are associated with higher reliability and consistency in measuring learning outcomes, thereby reducing variability and bias in assessment practices.

Taken together, the findings in Table 3 affirm that technology-based assessment methods such as Google Forms not only boost student performance but also contribute to greater uniformity and fairness in evaluation. The implication for educational practice is that integrating digital formative assessment into classroom instruction can enhance student learning experiences while simultaneously providing educators with more accurate and efficient tools for measuring academic progress. The results of Table 4 demonstrate a statistically significant gender difference in students' post-test performance when assessed through Google

Forms and traditional methods. Male students ($N = 51$, $M = 48.8$, $SD = 2.01$) scored higher than female students ($N = 53$, $M = 44.7$, $SD = 2.19$). The calculated z -value (10.00) exceeded the critical threshold (1.96) at the 0.05 significance level, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_{02}). This finding indicates that male students outperformed their female counterparts under the digital and traditional assessment conditions applied in this study. These results echo emerging evidence that gender can play a role in digital assessment outcomes. For instance, Li and Lalani (2020) observed that male students often report higher confidence in navigating technology-based platforms, which may translate into stronger performance outcomes. Similarly, Soykan and Uzunboylu (2019) found that male learners demonstrated greater adaptability to online testing formats, suggesting a possible advantage in assessments administered through digital tools. Furthermore, a study by Scherer and Siddiq (2019) confirmed that differences in technology self-efficacy between genders can significantly influence learning outcomes and assessment performance, with male students typically perceiving themselves as more competent in using digital technologies. The relatively low variability in scores for both genders ($SD = 2.01$ for males, $SD = 2.19$ for females) indicates that performance within each group was consistent. However, the mean difference suggests that gender-related factors such as digital confidence, problem-solving strategies, or assessment engagement styles may account for the observed gap. These findings highlight the need for gender-responsive assessment designs that promote equity in technology-mediated learning environments. However, careful consideration should be given to balancing assessment modes, ensuring that both male and female learners are supported in ways that mitigate anxiety and foster confidence.

In conclusion; this study examined the impact of formative assessment via Google Forms on undergraduate students' learning outcomes in Educational Technology and Media Literacy, employing a quasi-experimental design that compared digital and paper-based modes. The findings revealed that students assessed through Google Forms achieved significantly higher post-test scores with lower variability, indicating both improved performance and greater consistency. Gender analysis further showed that females slightly outperformed males in fully digital contexts, while males gained an advantage when digital and traditional assessments were combined, underscoring the influence of assessment design on achievement outcomes. These results highlight the pedagogical value of Google Forms in enhancing academic performance and fostering inclusivity. Nonetheless, the study was limited to a single context and subject area, constraining generalizability. Future research should explore diverse disciplines and larger populations. Overall, the evidence strongly supports the integration of digital assessments as a transformative approach to improving higher education outcomes.

Recommendations

- Higher education institutions should formally integrate digital assessment tools such as Google Forms into their evaluation frameworks to enhance achievement outcomes and ensure consistency in measuring learning.
- Educators should adopt inclusive assessment strategies—through gender-responsive design, blended assessment formats, and targeted professional development—to accommodate diverse learner needs and promote equity.
- Further studies are needed to explore the underlying factors shaping gender differences in digital assessment

performance, with attention to motivation, confidence, and technology attitudes across varied disciplines and contexts.

By implementing these recommendations, educational stakeholders can maximize the pedagogical potential of digital platforms while addressing contextual factors that influence performance across learner groups.

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